

A STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF STARCH TEMPERATURE CHANGES ON PACKAGING PAPER PRODUCTION IN SIZE PRESS MACHINE

Tamer Sözbir¹

tamersozbir@kmpaper.com

Cihangir H. Oba¹

chakanoba@kmpaper.com

Ahmet Tutuş²

atutus@ksu.edu.tr

(ORC-ID: 0000-0003-2922-4916)

Mustafa Çiçekler²

mcicekler@ksu.edu.tr

(ORC-ID: 0000-0001-5793-2827)

¹ *KMKPaper Co., R&D Center, Kahramanmaraş, Turkey*

² *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Faculty of Forestry, Department of Forest Industry Engineering, Kahramanmaraş, Turkey*

Abstract

In this study, effect of temperature on the use of starch in packaging paper production and to find optimum use of starch, the properties of starch such as dry matter amount, viscosity and pH value were evaluated by continuously measuring. Fluting (90 gr/m²), NSSC (120 gr/m²) and Test liner (110 gr/m²) paper types using waste paper as raw material were selected as the most common production types and their strength values were measured. All production conditions were kept constant and measurements were made by changing the starch temperature in the size press equipment. Starch obtained from natural corn was used in the size press. According to obtained data, it was measured that as a result of the increase in starch temperature from 70 °C to 75 °C, strength values such as burst, CMT and SCT increased by 6% in all paper types. When the temperature was increased to 80 °C, it was determined that there was an 18% increase compared to 70 °C. In addition, porosity values of the papers decreased by 7-10% with increasing temperature. At temperatures above 80 °C, it occurred defects in the paper and problems with sticking to the felts in the machine became difficult to control.

Keywords: Starch, temperature, packaging paper, strength

1. Introduction

In paper and board production, waste paper efficiency and quality is a very important issue, especially in paper machines that produce using 100% waste paper. In general, it is one of the most important and major factors affecting the quality and cost of the produced paper. Since there is no packaging paper production using 100% cellulose in Turkey, the papers consist of waste papers that are recycled in the same process. In each paper and board recycling cycle, the fibers in the paper and board are shortened and weakened (Edinger, 2004). This creates a strength problem in the paper production. Some auxiliary substances are used in the production of paper and board to alleviate such problems. Among these, the most commonly used material is starch (Özden and Sönmez, 2019). The place where starch is used in paper production is 'Size Press' equipment, this equipment is

composed of 2 coated cylinders and hydraulically presses on paper to increase the penetration of starch into paper (Smook, 1994; Knowpap, 2013).

Starch must also go through some processes in order to be used in the production and to reach size press equipment (Özden and Sönmez, 2019). The starch preparation tank is first filled with cold water and starch is poured into the tank filled with water according to the dry matter amount of the starch mixture to be made. By injecting steam into the tank, the starch mixture is brought to a temperature of 95 °C at a suitable mixing speed and cooked for 10 minutes, so that the starch molecules absorb the water and come to a gel form. Then, while the mixing process continues at this temperature, it is rested for 10 minutes and at the end of this process, the starch solution is sent to the stock tank. The stock tank is double-walled and there are steam pipes between the two walls, so that the starch solution is kept warm. The starch solution is sent from the stock tank to the second stock tank under the press equipment, which is the end-use place, during this process, the starch temperature decreases due to the intermediate distance. Here, the starch temperature varies between 65-70 °C. Such a decrease in the temperature of the starch solution at the end-use area negatively affects the starch viscosity and indirectly its penetration into the paper, which has a negative effect on the strength values of the final product (Zijderveld and Stoutjesdijk, 1976; Andersen, 1997). In addition, if the starch mixture is not at the desired high temperature, the problem of sticking to the cylinder surface arises because the starch called 'picking' in the drying cylinder where the paper is first contacted after the press equipment where the starch is applied cannot penetrate well into the paper (Maurer, 2001).

Today, as a result of the decreasing waste paper quality and increasingly need for stronger paper, paper mills prefer to use starch as the most economical and efficient way to produce strength paper. Literature studies have shown that in order for starch to have a better effect on paper, the starch temperature must be kept at the highest possible level and used at that temperature. In this study, it was aimed to determine the process equipment required to increase the temperature of starch at the size press and apply it stably on paper and to determine the effects of starch temperature on the final paper produced. In addition to the temperature, in order to find an optimum use value, the starch properties such as dry matter amount, viscosity, and pH value were continuously measured and evaluated.

2. Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in Kahramanmaraş Paper Mill under the coordination of R&D unit. The modifications within the scope of the study were carried out in two stages. In line with the plans made according to the purpose of the study, the current situation was determined first and then a redesign was made in the conventional size press machine (Fig. 1) for the desired purpose. With the completion of these studies, trials have been carried out.

Figure 2. Conventional starch application workflow at size press

In the study, three different packaging papers were produced: Fluting (90 g/m²), (NSSC 120 g/m²) and Test liner (110 g/m²). During the production, waste papers, fennopol 351, fennopol 326, silica (fennosil 2180), CK Floc 640 (Polydadmec), cationic starch (Hi-Cat 643A), natural starch, nopcomaster ENA 475, papertreat PD and chlorine dioxide were used. The changes in viscosity properties by heating starch to 60-70-75-80 °C temperatures were also investigated. At temperatures above 80 °C, it occurred defects in the paper and problems with sticking to the felts in the machine became difficult to control. The penetration of starch into paper was also calculated.

Some physical and strength properties of the packaging papers were determined and tests and standards were given in Table 1.

Table 6. Some physical and strength tests and standards applied to the packaging papers

Tests	Standards
Burst Strength (kPa)	TS EN ISO 2758
CMT (Corrugated Medium Test)	TS EN ISO 7263
CCT (Concora Corrugated Test)	TS 12735
SCT (Short Span Compressive Test)	TS ISO 9895
RCT (Ring Crush Test)	TS 12734
Scott Bond (Internal Bond Test)	TAPPI 569
Porosity	TS ISO 5636-5
Filler Content	TS 1683
COBB (Water Absorbency Test)	TS EN ISO 535

Ten test papers were produced from the pulps obtained from each experiment and arithmetic means of the data were used for evaluation of the study.

3. Results and Discussion

The properties of the starch such as dry matter, consumption and viscosity at different temperatures were given in Table 2 below.

Table 7. Some properties of the starch at different temperatures

Paper Type	Starch Properties	Temperature (°C)			
		60	70	75	80
Fluting	Dry Matter (%)	10.5	10.5	10.5	10.5
	Starch Consumption (gr/m ²)	3.6	3.68	3.7	3.74
	Viscosity (Pa.s)	82	74	71	66
NSSC	Dry Matter (%)	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
	Starch Consumption (gr/m ²)	6.1	6.21	6.25	6.29
	Viscosity (Pa.s)	78	74	71	63
Test Liner	Dry Matter (%)	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5
	Starch Consumption (gr/m ²)	5.01	5.14	5.21	5.25
	Viscosity (Pa.s)	76	70	68	65

Dry matters of the starches used in fluting, NSSC, and test liner papers were kept constant as 10.5%, 9.0%, and 7.5%, respectively. Generally, starch consumption rates increased with the increase in temperature of the starch at size press in production of all paper types. Moreover, viscosity values decreased due to the increases in starch temperature.

The physical and strength properties of the fluting papers with 90 (gr/m²) grammages were present in Table 3.

Table 8. Some physical and strength properties of the fluting papers produced with using starch at different temperatures

Starch Temperatures (°C)	60	70	75	80
Burst Strength (kPa)	1.72	1.75	1.81	1.93
CMT (N)	150	162	178	186
CCT (kN/m)	1.20	1.29	1.35	1.43
SCT (kN/m)	1.21	1.29	1.32	1.42
Porosity (s)	43	42	40	37
Filler Content (%)	14.5	14.6	14.5	14.4

In Table 3, it can be observed that with the increase in starch temperature at size press, the properties of the fluting papers have improved. With the increase of starch temperature from 60 °C to 80 °C, burst strength, CMT, CCT and SCT values increased by 12.2%, 24%, 19.2% and 17.4%, respectively. Besides, the surface properties of the fluting papers have been positively affected by the application of starch at high temperatures at the size press. The porosity of the fluting papers decreased to 37 s by increasing the applied starch temperature to 80 °C at size press.

The physical and strength properties of the NSSC papers with 120 (gr/m²) grammages were present in Table 4.

Table 9. Some physical and strength properties of the NSSC papers produced with using starch at different temperatures

Starch Temperatures (°C)	60	70	75	80
Burst Strength (kPa)	2.36	2.40	2.61	2.80
CMT (N)	290	295	307	332
CCT(kN/m)	2.01	2.01	2.11	2.29
SCT(kN/m)	1.85	1.87	1.90	1.99
Porosity (s)	36	34	34	33
Filler Content (%)	16.4	16.5	16.4	16.5
COBB ₆₀ (gr/m ²)	35	35	36	34

According to Table 4, NSSC paper properties were enhanced with increasing starch temperature at size press. However, the use of starch at different temperatures had no significant effect on the COBB values of NSSC papers. With the increase of the starch temperature at the size press from 60 °C to 80 °C, the burst strength, CMT, CCT and SCT values of the NSSC papers increased by 18.6%, 14.5%, 13.9% and 7.6%, respectively, while the porosity values decreased by 8.3%.

In Table 5, physical and strength properties of test liner papers with 120 (gr/m²) grammages produced by applying starch at different temperatures were given.

Table 10. Some physical and strength properties of the test liner papers produced with using starch at different temperatures

	60	70	75	80
Burst Strength (kPa)	2.30	2.30	2.60	2.80
RCT (kN/m)	0.78	0.80	0.81	0.83
SCT(kN/m)	1.79	1.80	1.83	1.90
Scott Bond(J/m ²)	556	563	581	506
Porosity	46	44	41	37
Filler Content (%)	15.5	15.4	15.5	15.4
COBB ₆₀ (gr/m ²)	32	31	31	32

In the table, it is seen that the properties of the test liner paper except Scott Bond and COBB values increased in parallel with the increase in starch temperature. The Scott Bond value of the test liner decreased approximately 5% when the temperature of the applied starch was 80 °C. However, when the temperature of the applied starch was 75 °C, the Scott Bond value of the test liner increased by approximately 4.5% compared to 60 °C. As with the COBB values of NSSC papers, it was determined that starch application at different temperatures did not have a significant effect on COBB values of the test liner papers. With increasing starch temperature at size press from 60 °C to 80 °C, burst strength, RCT and SCT values of the test liner papers were increased about 21.7%, 6.4% and 6.1%, respectively. Porosity values of the test liner papers decreased from 46 to 37 by increasing starch temperature at the size press.

4. Discussion

In Table 2, it is seen that starch consumption increases and viscosity decreases depending on the temperature increase. Adhesion of starch applied at high temperature increases within the paper (Hedenqvist, 2002). Thus, an increase is observed in the rate of starch adhering to the paper surface at size press. Viscosity of starch solution has an

important role in paper production in order to obtain smooth and strength paper (Clerck, 1991). The temperature applied in the preparation of the starch solution directly affects the viscosity (Harvey and Welling, 1976; Choudhury and Patel, 1992). High viscosity starch solutions cause problems at size press applications. It causes the formation of a sticky line between the starch application roller and the rapidly moving paper surface. In this case, which is called as "size pick up", the paper is in a sense separating from the size press, causing problems (adhesion), stresses and sometimes ruptures occur in the paper (Andersen, 1997). As a result, the high starch temperature applied at the size press section can provide the solution of the above mentioned problems.

In the production of packaging paper, as the temperature of the starch applied in the press increased, the physical and strength properties improved. The purpose of using starch in paper production is to improve the strength properties of the paper (Zijderveld and Stoutjesdijk, 1976). Therefore, the adhesion of starch to the surface of the paper has also increased the strength values of the paper (Maurer, 2001). In Table 2, it can be seen that as the application temperature of the starch applied to paper increased, the adhesion rate increased. One of the factors affecting burst strength is fiber length and the other is internal bonding (Clark, 1978; Erođlu, 2003). Since starch applied at high temperature penetrates better into paper, an increase in burst strength is achieved. The attachment of cationic starch to cellulose is explained by the ionic interaction that occurs between the cationic groups and the acidic groups of the cellulose. However, hydrogen bonding to a lesser extent also plays a role in starch adsorption (Ondaral, S., 2012).

Other properties of the packaging papers such as CMT, CCT, SCT and RCT were also higher with high temperature starch application as well as burst strength. One of the most important properties affected by the application of starch to paper at size press is porosity, i.e. surface roughness (Maurer, 2009). When the tables given above are examined, the increases in the starch application temperature decreased the porosity values of the produced packaging papers. One of the problems encountered during the separation of the paper from the size press after the starch is applied to the paper is the picking. In this case, one of the solutions can be applied, such as lowering the machine speed, lowering the viscosity (diluting the starch) or heating the starch solution (Andersen, 1997).

5. Conclusion

It has been observed that some physical and strength properties of the packaging papers were improved with using starch at 80 °C. It was also determine that the high temperature of the starch solution applied on the paper eliminates the problems such as degradation, picking and rupture that at the size press occur. Increases in the temperature of the starch solution applied provide both more starch penetration into the paper and ease of application. It is possible to produce high strength paper by increasing the starch temperature applied at the size press without using any extra chemicals and raw materials. As a result of this study, application of the starch solution at 80 °C in the size press section gives optimum results.

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References

- Andersen J. (1997). *Surface Sizing, Surface Application of Paper*. London: Ed. Brander, J. and Thorn, Blackie Academic & Profesional.
- Choudhury K.C. and Patel M. (1992). Gelatinization of Starch and Surface Sizing. *IPPTA*, 4(4), 21-26.
- Clark J.A. (1978). *Pulp Technology*, Mille Freeman Publications, Inc. California.
- Clerck P. (1991). Surface Sizing Basic. *Asia Pacific Pulp and Paper*, 3, 15-18.
- Edinger G. (2004). *Waste Paper. Papier aus Osterreich*, 11, 24.
- Eroğlu H. (2003). *Paper and Paper Physics Lecture Notes*, 144 pages, Trabzon, Turkey.
- Harvey R.D. and Welling L.J. (1976) Viscosity Stabilizer for High Solids Thermal-chemically Converted Starch Pastes Used as Coating Adhesives. *Tappi Coating COnf. Proc.*, 53-59.
- Hedenqvist M. (2020). *Mechanical Properties of Polymers; Viscoelastic Properties*. Course compendium, Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm.
- Knowpap, (2013). *Paperitekniiikan ja automation oppimisympäristö*. VTT. Versio 15.0. Viitattu 20.4.2014. <http://www.jamk.fi/fi/Palvelut/kirjasto/Etusivu/> , Nelli-portaali, Knowpa.
- Maurer H.W. (2001). *Manufacture and Composition of Unmodified Starch*, in *Starch and Starch Product in Surface Sizing and Paper Coating*, Chapter 4. Tappi Press, USA, 25-29.
- Maurer H.W. (2009). *Starch in the Paper Industry*, in *Starch Chemistry and Technology*, Chapter 18. James BeMiller and Roy Whistler (eds.), Academic Press, USA, 693-695.
- Ondaral S. (2012). *Paper Chemicals Textbook*, Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Forestry, Trabzon, Turkey.
- Özden Ö. Sönmez S. (2019). *Starch Usage in Paper Industry*. In *Research & Reviews in Engineering*, Ed. Mahmut Turhan, Gece Akademi Publications, 209-223, Turkey.
- Smook, G.A., (1994). *Handbook for Pulp & Paper Technologists*. Vancouver: Angus Wilde Publications, p. 283.
- Zijderveld A.H. and Stoutjesdijk P.G. (1976). *The Paper Industry*, in *Industrial Uses of Starch and Its Derivatives*, Chapter 5. J. A. Radley, Applied Science Publishers Ltd., London, 199-209.